

Research Station Canning, West Bengal. The trial was in a randomized block design replicated 3 times in a 1-m-deep plot. All 30 entries were sown 22 Jun 1984 and transplanted on 23 Aug. Each entry was transplanted in 4 rows, at 30 hills/row. Spacing between rows and plants was 30 cm. Standing water depth at transplanting was 12 cm and surface soil (0-15 cm) salinity (EC_{sw}) in situ was 9.0 dS/m. Standing water depth during

crop growth was 29-58 cm in Aug, 47-50 cm in Sep, 41-51 cm in Oct, and 38 cm in Nov and Dec. The crop was harvested in Jan 1985.

Survival rate of the plants that survived to maturity ranged from 4 to 95% (see table). RPAR7360 and PLAI 100 did not survive. NC540 had maximum survival of 95%, followed by NC491 with 91%. Panicles/ m² ranged from 47 to 142, with NC492 producing

the most. CR292-5258 produced 135 panicles/m², but it also exhibited maximum spikelet sterility (77.6%). Kalamota (sel) had 68% survival and 105 panicles/m², whereas Pankaj had a survival rate of 68% and produced 75 panicles/m². The three highest yielding entries were NC491, 780 g/plot; SR26B, 743 g/plot; and NC487/77, 490 g/plot. Local check Kalamota (sel) yielded 392 g/plot. *ℓ*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

HYBRID RICE

Utilization of wide compatibility gene (S_5^n) for rice breeding

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F₁ hybrids of indica-japonica crosses show semisterility, while some wide compatibility varieties (WCVs) produce fertile F₁ plants when crossed with indica or with japonica varieties. We analyzed the genetic base for F₁ sterility and wide compatibility as follows. A set of multiple alleles was located between the *C* (chromogen for apiculus color) and *wx* (waxy endosperm) loci; S_5^n for WCVs, S_5^i for indica varieties, and S_5^j for japonica varieties, and the genotypes of S_5^n/S_5^i and S_5^n/S_5^j were fertile, but S_5^i/S_5^j was semisterile because of partial abortion of gametes carrying S_5^j . So far, some javanicas or derivatives such as Ketan Nangka, Calotoc, and CPSLO 17 have been found to possess S_5^n , and they also have the complementary genes for apiculus color, i.e. C^+ and A^+ . Since C^+ is closely linked with S_5^n , the progeny of indica/ WCVs or japonica/ WCVs showing apiculus color are likely to possess S_5^n .

We have selected several lines from Ketan Nangka (KN) crosses. The progeny of IR50//IR36/ Ketan Nangka showed indica-like plant type as well as good fertility of F₁ when crossed with japonica testers (see table). Likewise, some lines selected from

Characteristics of some promising lines with wide compatibility gene S_5^n , 1986.

Line	Cross or variety	Generation	Flowering date	Plant ht (cm)	F ₁ fertility	
					Tester	Fertility (%)
A1	Akihikari/NK4 ^a	F ₅	20 May	94	IR50	89.4
A9	Akihikari/NK4	F ₅	22 May	87	IR50	85.4
B5	Akihikari//Akihikari/NK4	F ₄	20 May	80	IR36	90.7
B20	Akihikari//Akihikari/NK4	F ₄	18 May	92	IR36	86.9
C1	IR50//IR36/Ketan Nangka	F ₅	29 May	92	Akihikari	83.5
C2	IR50//IR36/Ketan Nangka	F ₅	29 May	98	Akihikari	90.3
	Ketan Nangka		15 Jun	158	IR36	88.2
	Toyonishiki (check)		21 May	88	Akihikari	93.4
	IR36 (check)		4 Jun	81		89.1
	IR50/Akihikari F ₁ (check)		(test in 1983)			42.8

^a NK4 is an F₆ line from Nihonmasari/Ketan Nangka.

Akihikari//Akihikari/ (a line from Nihonmasari/ Ketan Nangka) showed normal F₁ fertility when crossed with IR36, although the lines are morphologically japonica type (see table).

The incorporation of S_5^n gene to indica or japonica breeding lines is expected to alleviate the sterility problem in indica-japonica crosses.

Specifically, those lines with S_5^n can be used for hybrid seed production, inasmuch as they would reveal high level of heterosis without F₁ sterility. As some IR varieties, including IR36 and IR50, possess a restorer gene for cytoplasmic male sterility of japonica type, indica-like lines with the S_5^n can be used directly as parents for hybrid seed production. *ℓ*

Pest Control and Management

DISEASES

Etiology of rice orange leaf

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In Thailand, Malaysia, and Indonesia, orange leaf is known to be associated

with mycoplasma-like organisms (MLO). Recent reports from China indicated that virus-like particles are associated with orange leaf.

We collected 34 rice plants with orange leaf-like symptoms from 6 Philippine sites. *Recilia dorsalis* nymphs